

BASIC PRINCIPLES OF DESIGNING PEDAGOGICAL ACTIVITIES

Gazieva L.A.

Teacher of the Tashkent State Pedagogical University named after Nizami

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Abstract. *The dissertation is dedicated to the exploration of designing pedagogical activities in the context of informatization. In today's society, information technology plays an increasingly important role in education, and educators need to adapt to these changes and utilize new opportunities for effective learning.*

The aim of this study is to investigate and describe the fundamental principles and methods of designing pedagogical activities in the context of educational informatization, using the teaching methodology of mathematics as an example. To achieve this aim, the following objectives were set:

- *analyzing current trends in educational informatization and approaches to designing pedagogical activities;*
- *identifying the peculiarities of educational informatization processes;*
- *studying the experience of applying information technology in pedagogical activities;*
- *establishing the scientific and applied foundations of designing pedagogical activities;*
- *identifying challenges and key strategies for enhancing the effectiveness of designing pedagogical activities.*

Throughout the research, a theoretical analysis and synthesis of literary sources were conducted. The main problems that educators face when using information technology in educational practice were identified, and recommendations for overcoming them were proposed.

As a result of the study, the most effective methodology for designing pedagogical activities in the context of informatization was determined. This methodology includes stages such as analyzing learning needs and goals, selecting and adapting information technology, developing and implementing educational materials, and assessing the effectiveness of the educational process.

The dissertation contributes to the development of theory and practice in designing pedagogical activities in the context of informatization. The research findings can be utilized by educators and professionals in the field of education to enhance the effectiveness of the educational process.

Keywords: *educational informatization, SMART principle, cognitive accessibility, teaching methods, visualization of material, adaptation of educational materials, Variability.*

The basic principles of designing pedagogical activities may vary depending on the specific approach or methodology, but there are some general principles that are widely used in pedagogy. Here are some of them:

1. Goal setting: defining specific learning goals and objectives that should be clear, measurable and achievable.

Goal setting allows you to determine the direction and content of the educational process, as well as evaluate its results.

When designing the teaching of mathematics, goal setting plays an important role. The teacher must clearly define what knowledge, skills and abilities he wants to convey to his students. For example, the goal may be the development of mathematical thinking, the formation of skills for solving mathematical problems, the mastery of specific mathematical concepts, etc.

Defining goals and objectives allows you to structure the educational material, select appropriate methods and forms of work, and evaluate the effectiveness of training. In addition, goal setting allows students to understand what they should achieve as a result of training and motivates them to actively study. It is important that goals and objectives are specific, measurable, achievable, relevant and time-bound (SMART principle). This approach allows you to more effectively plan and implement the process of teaching mathematics, as well as evaluate the results of training.

2. Individualization: taking into account the individual characteristics, needs, level of knowledge and interests of each student, adapting the educational process to the individual capabilities of each student.

Designing individualized pedagogical activity begins with diagnostics. The teacher must analyze the level of knowledge and skills of each student in order to determine their individual needs and capabilities. Based on the results of the diagnostics, individual learning plans are developed for each student, taking into account their abilities, conditions are created for individual work, providing various materials, tasks and teaching methods.

Results are controlled through constant monitoring of each student's progress in order to assess the effectiveness of individualized work and make the necessary adjustments. When assessing the achievements of each student, it is necessary to take into account their individual characteristics and progress. Individualization allows the teacher to adapt the educational process to each student, creating conditions for their successful learning and development. This helps to increase student motivation, improve results and create a positive educational environment.

3. Systematicity: organization of the educational process based on a logical sequence and connection between various elements of the educational program. It involves organizing the educational process as a holistic system and includes such aspects as integrity (the educational process should be organized in such a way that students see the connection between various mathematical topics and are able to apply the acquired knowledge and skills in various contexts), structure (mathematical material should be systematized and organized in a logical sequence so that the student can gradually assimilate and deepen his knowledge), interconnection (the teacher should help students see the connection between mathematical concepts and apply them in solving various problems and situations),

hierarchy (mathematical material should be organized by levels of complexity so that students can gradually develop their skills and competencies) and a systemic approach (the teacher should apply a systemic approach in their teaching activities, taking into account the interrelationship and interaction of various elements of the educational process). The principle of systematicity helps the teacher create a structured and holistic educational environment that promotes effective acquisition of mathematical knowledge and the development of mathematical competence in students.

4. Accessibility: creating conditions for equal access to education for all students, regardless of their social, economic or cultural status.

This means that educational processes and conditions must be accessible and inclusive for all participants in the educational process, regardless of their individual characteristics, abilities, needs and opportunities.

This principle implies the creation of equal opportunities for all students, including children with special educational needs, children with disabilities, children with different linguistic, cultural and social characteristics.

The following aspects of accessibility should be taken into account in the design of pedagogical activities:

physical accessibility - ensuring the accessibility of the physical environment for all participants in the educational process, including students with limited mobility. This may include accessible premises, lifts, ramps, special equipment, etc.;

cognitive accessibility - creating conditions for understanding and assimilating educational material by all students, including those with cognitive disabilities. This may include the use of various teaching methods, visualization of material, adaptation of educational materials, etc.;

- social accessibility - creating conditions for the inclusion of all participants in the educational process in the social environment, ensuring equal opportunities for communication and interaction. This may include organizing group work, joint projects, creating a friendly atmosphere, etc.;

- technological accessibility - the use of modern technologies and tools to ensure the accessibility of the educational process. This may include the use of special software, adapted devices, online resources, etc. The principle of accessibility in the design of pedagogical activities helps to create an inclusive educational environment where each student has equal opportunities for learning, development and success.

5. Activity: stimulating the active position of students in the learning process, developing their independence, creative thinking and research activity.

This principle assumes that students should be active participants in the lesson, involved in solving problems and building mathematical models.

To apply the principle of activity in the design of the pedagogical activity of a mathematics teacher, the following approaches can be used:

- problem-searching - the teacher formulates a problem or task that students must solve independently or in groups. This allows students to actively explore mathematical phenomena, apply the acquired knowledge in practice and develop their problem-solving skills;

- project-based activities - the teacher invites students to develop and implement a project related to mathematics. This can be creating a model, conducting research or developing a mathematical game. Project-based activities allow students to apply knowledge in real situations, develop creative thinking and independence;

- collective discussion and problem solving - the teacher offers students a problem that they solve together, discussing various ways of solving it and arguing their decisions. This helps develop communication skills, analytical thinking and the ability to work together.

The principle of activity in the design of the pedagogical activity of a mathematics teacher contributes to the development of students, helps them better understand mathematical concepts and apply them in practice.

6. Variability: using a variety of methods, forms and means of teaching to take into account the different learning styles and preferences of students.

Variability implies that the teacher should offer different options for tasks, methods and forms of work so that each student can choose a suitable way to solve a problem or learn the material. This allows the teacher to take into account the individual characteristics of each student, their level of knowledge, interests, ways of thinking and preferences.

The principle of variability helps to create conditions for active and independent work of students, develops their creative thinking, and promotes the formation of skills and abilities for solving mathematical problems independently.

The teacher can use various methods and techniques, such as a differentiated approach, group and individual work, the use of various teaching materials and technologies.

Variability also allows the teacher to adapt the teaching material to the specific conditions and needs of the study group, taking into account the differences in the level of preparation of students, their interests and methods of learning.

The application of the principle of variability in the design of the pedagogical activity of a mathematics teacher contributes to more effective and individualized learning, increases the motivation and interest of students in studying mathematics.

7. Dialogism: active interaction between the teacher and students, as well as between the students themselves, in order to create an atmosphere of mutual respect, support and cooperation.

The teacher must create conditions for the active participation of students in class and extracurricular activities, stimulate their independence, initiative and creative thinking, be able to effectively conduct a dialogue with students, ask questions, provoke them to discuss mathematical problems and issues. It is also important to provide feedback so that students understand their mistakes and can correct them.

In addition, it is necessary to take into account the individual characteristics of each student, their level of preparation and interests, create conditions for cooperation and joint participation of students in solving mathematical problems and projects. This helps to develop communication skills, the ability to work in a team and share experiences.

The teacher should encourage students to think critically, analyze and evaluate mathematical problems and solutions. It is important to teach students to argue their thoughts and express their point of view. The principle of dialogism helps to create a favorable educational environment in which students actively participate in the learning process and develop their mathematical skills and competencies.

8. Assessment and feedback: systematically assessing students' learning achievements and providing them with feedback to support their further development.

This principle is an important component of successful learning. Assessment in the design of the pedagogical activity of a mathematics teacher can be different: formative (direct feedback during the learning process), summative (assessment of learning results) and diagnostic (analysis of the level of knowledge and skills of students before the start of learning).

The principle of assessment allows the teacher to assess the effectiveness of his teaching, as well as to identify the successes and difficulties of students, adapt his methods and approaches in accordance with the needs of students and help them achieve their goals.

Feedback is an integral part of the assessment process. It is given by the teacher to the students and contains information about achievements, progress and areas for improvement. Feedback can be either verbal or written and should be constructive, understandable and motivating for the students. The principle of assessment and feedback helps to create a favorable

educational environment in which students can develop and achieve success. It helps to increase the motivation and self-esteem of students, and also allows the teacher to continuously improve his/her work.

These are just some of the principles that can be used in the design of pedagogical activities. It is important to remember that each teacher can develop their own principles based on their experience and unique working conditions.

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